

Application of Porters Strategic Concept: Study of Awareness and Application by Senior Marketing Executives in Pune, India

Somnath Patil¹ and Vishal Wadajkar²

¹Associate Professor, Dr. D. Y. Patil Institute of Management & Research, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

²Assistant Professor, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

CITATION: Patil, Somnath and Wadajkar, Vishal (2017), "Application of Porters Strategic Concept: Study of Awareness and Application by Senior Marketing Executives in Pune, India", *MERC Global's International Journal of Management*, Vol. 5, Issue 4, pp. 143-146.

ARTICLE HISTORY: Submitted: April 10, 2017, Revision received: June 30, 2017, Accepted: July 14, 2017

ARTICLE TYPE: Research paper

ABSTRACT

This is a descriptive study to assess the variables of awareness and application of Porter's strategic concept of business using a survey questionnaire. Descriptive hypotheses were set and studied based on primary data collected from 100 senior marketing executives from Pune. They were surveyed from different companies on the awareness and application level of Porter's Strategic Concept in their actual work. Both awareness and application were measured on a 5-point Likert scale for responses to 10 items under each variable. Sample means were compared against the hypothesized population means of the scale midpoint of 2 and were tested for statistical significance at the 95 % confidence level. The study disclosed that both the sample means for awareness and application were statistically significant, albeit on opposite sides. While the awareness mean was found to be well above the hypothesized population mean, the application level mean was found to be considerably lower than the hypothesized population mean. While the total awareness level was found to be statistically significant (Mean = 3.18; SD = 0.87), the total application level was found to be low at (Mean = 1.52; SD = 0.79). The study results indicate that Porter's strategic concepts are not yet well implemented despite good awareness. They remain in the books; in practice, managers do not apply them.

KEYWORDS: Competitive advantage, Porters' strategic concept, Awareness, Application.

1. INTRODUCTION

Competition in any business is the fundamental variable for the success or failure of its enterprise. Porter (1985) researched the importance of competitive strategy as the baseline for performance activities in a company encompassing innovation, stable culture, an exemplary implementation for a lucrative and viable position in the industry.

He based his theory on five rules of competitiveness, i.e. new competitors, the buyer's bargaining power, the threat of substitutes, bargaining power of suppliers, and rivalry of competitors. These five rules play an essential part in any firm's ability to earn back the cost of the capital and investment on their returns.

Another critical aspect of the competitive strategy is the firm's placement at an above-average vantage point, according to its profitability in the industry and is called a competitive advantage of a particular company. It is based on three basic generic strategies: cost leadership, differentiation, and focus. Where leadership cost is to keep the cost of production low with low overheads and efficient training of staff and higher returns, differentiation is that the firm is exclusive on some dimensions in

its industry that can be valued by its buyers who are even ready to pay a premium price for its products and finally focus is for a target set of exclusive customer segment where the firm comes up with a different strategy to serve their needs (Porter 1985).

Therefore, based on these examples, we decided to survey senior marketing executives from Pune from different companies on the awareness and application level of Porter's Strategic Concept in their actual work to achieve the desired business results. The research question to be addressed is as follows:

RQ: Is there a reasonable awareness and application of Porter's Strategic Competitiveness among senior marketing executives in Pune, India?

The term "reasonable" was operationalized at the mid-point of a 5-point Likert scale at the value of $(0+1+2+3+4)/5=2$, with 0 indicating Not at all aware/Not at all used and four indicating Highly aware/Widely used.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A successful business organization needs strategic planning that is, as defined by Stacey (2000) - "the process of actively participating in the conversation around important emerging issues" and its implementation that is -"creation of unique and valuable position involving a different set of activities" (Porter, 1996).

The crux of the strategy is dependent on the awareness and application by its stakeholders, which translates into an economic advantage, allocation of resources, and guides the firm's assessment regarding its organization and management (Walker, 2004).

A study by Kinyuira (2014) has exemplified that the pursuit of Porter's generic strategies can enhance cost leadership, differentiation and focus, and the overall performance of Savings and Credit Cooperatives in Saccos (Kenya). Another study done by Indiaty *et al.* (2014) has shown a strong relationship ($R=0.8$) between the Porters 5 forces model and the performance of a cooperative bank in Kenya, especially on the variables of bargaining powers of buyers and sellers in the banking industry.

Porter's theories have been applied in Kenya for the Matatu (low-cost minibus) transport industry. They have to constantly reinvent themselves against their competitors within the given limitation of input capital crunch by employing better drivers and touts for attracting customers daily (Naku, 2011). The other example is from the banking sector in Kenya, where the competitive strategy is used in the multinational banks to maintain their stature in the market. This study was a survey of managers of 18 multinational banks in Kenya and what competitive strategy they use for their customer service differentiation based on their tastes and preferences to maintain their customers. The study results found that setting up a research department in their organization helps understand its customers' needs better.

A contextual research gap exists, and hence this study was undertaken by surveying senior marketing professionals.

3. METHODS

The research methodology adopted is outlined below:

- A survey questionnaire was administered to 100 (Bullen, 2016) senior marketing executives.
- The selection of the 100 senior marketing executives was based on the writer's judgment of getting an adequate response in a reasonable time. Convenience sampling was used. For this purpose, networking of the writer friends
- The survey questionnaire was divided into two parts: a. Measurement of awareness level and b. Measurement of application level
- Ten concepts were framed, and responses were sought on Likert scales in two sections: awareness level and application level.
- For assessment of awareness levels, the scale used was: 0-Not at all aware, 1-Little bit aware, 2-Somewhat aware, 3-Well aware, 4-Highly aware. The ten items of the Awareness level

were: Aw1: Economics of Scale, Aw2: Proprietary product differences, Aw3: Brand identity, Aw4: Switching costs; Aw5: Capital requirements, Aw6: Access to distribution, Aw7: Absolute cost advantages, Aw8: Proprietary learning curve, Aw9: Access, Aw10: Necessary inputs (Porter, 1985).

- For assessment of application levels, the scale used was: 0-Not at all used, 1-Used a little bit, 2-Used somewhat, 3-Used well, 4-Used widely. As stated in the awareness, the ten items were assessed for the application level (Porter, 1985).

3.1 Statement of hypotheses

H₀₁: The awareness level about Porter's strategic concepts is reasonable.

H_{a1}: The knowledge level about Porter's strategic concepts is better than reasonable.

H₀₂: These concepts are applied in practice as well at a reasonable level.

H_{a2}: These concepts in practice are not applied at a reasonable level.

Data analysis included descriptive analysis specifying features of the sample and inferential analysis to test the hypotheses. A t-test was used because the SD of the population is not known, in which case, a Z-test could have been applied. A t-test in practice is widely used as a substitute for the Z-test wherein the SD of the sample is taken as the SD of the population (given unknown population SD).

The survey instrument returned a Cronbach's alpha of 0.88, which is better than 0.70 (the standard) and hence was considered reliable.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive analysis

52 out of the 100 senior marketing executive respondents surveyed were male, while 48 were female. Thirty-six marketing professionals belonged to the age group <40 years, 29 were from the age group 40-50, while 35 were from the age group >50 years. Thirty-five marketing professionals reported work experience in the range of 10-15 years, 48 in the range of 15-20 years, and 17 had work experience of more than 20 years. Seventy-four respondents were from the manufacturing sector, while 26 were from the service sector.

4.2 Inferential analysis

The null hypotheses were set as the sample mean (\bar{x}) equals the hypothesized population mean (μ). The alternate hypotheses were: Ha1: $\bar{x} > 2$ and Ha2: $\bar{x} < 2$. These were set based on the common knowledge that there is a big gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. A summary of the ratings for the awareness levels is given in Table 1 below:

Concepts	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Total
Average awareness rating	3.28	3.19	3.15	3.16	3.29	3.14	3.14	3.16	3.25	3.13	3.19

A summary of the ratings for the application levels is given in Table 2 below:

Concepts	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Total
Average application rating	1.42	1.56	1.47	1.63	1.56	1.51	1.36	1.61	1.64	1.5	1.53

Table 3 shows the testing of the two hypotheses at a 95% confidence level.

Both the null hypotheses were rejected in favour of the alternate that the sample means are significantly different from the hypothesized population means.

Parameter	H ₁ value	H ₂ value
Sample Mean (\bar{x})	3.19	1.53
The hypothesized population mean (μ)	2.00	2.00
SD of sample	0.87	0.79
n (sample size)	100	100
t-value= $\text{abs}(\bar{x} - \mu) / (s/\sqrt{n})$	13.67816	5.949367
p-value = $\text{tdist}(t,(n-1),1)$	0.00000	0.00000
Decision	Reject Null	Reject Null

The sample mean for awareness was 3.19 (SD = 0.87) on a maximum scale of 4 and was significantly higher than a reasonable level assumed at the mid-point of the scale, that is, 2. Interestingly, the sample mean for the application was only 1.53 (SD = 0.79) on a maximum scale of 4 and was significantly lower than a reasonable level assumed at the mid-point of the scale, that is, 2. The gap between the awareness mean of 3.19 and the application mean of 1.53 is 1.66, 52% of the awareness level.

5. CONCLUSION

The study shows the ever classic reality of a high level of theoretical knowledge going hand-in-hand with poor levels of practical application. It, in other words, exposes the lack of "application skills." Porter's strategic framework concepts are time-tested and have been accepted the world over as "rules" of strategy formulation. But the problem comes with the application. A particular skill is required to implement the concepts in practice, failing which, such gaps between awareness and application will always be there. As the study was based on sampling, limitations of sampling, in general, apply to it as well. Researchers are encouraged to find out what it takes to apply the concepts in practice apart from its knowledge.

6. REFERENCES

1. Bullen, P. B. (2016), How to choose a sample size (for the statistically challenged), accessed from: <http://www.tools4dev.org/resources/how-to-choose-a-sample-size/>.
2. Dhotre, Meenal and Raje, Prakash (2014), "Application of Porter's Five Forces Model in the BPM Industry", *MERC Global's International Journal of Management*, Vol. 2, Issue 2, pp. 51-65.
3. Indiaty, C. M.; Mucheru, Stephen Mwangi; Evans, Nyamboga Mandere; Julius, Miroga Bichanga and Gongera, Enock George (2014), "The Application of Porter's Five Forces Model on Organization Performance: A Case of Cooperative Bank of Kenya Ltd.", *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 6, No. 16.
4. Kinyuira, D. (2014), "Effects of Porter's Generic Competitive Strategies on the Performance of Savings and Credit Cooperatives (Saccos) in Murang'a County, Kenya", *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 16, Issue 6, pp. 93-105.
5. Naku, P. (2011), Application of Porter's Competitive Strategies in the Matatu transport industry in Nairobi, Kenya (Dissertation).
6. Ogotu, O. and Nyatichi, V. (2012), "Competitive Strategies Adopted by Multinational Banks in Kenya", *DBA Africa Management Review*, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 98-109.
7. Porter, M. E. (1985), *Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance*, The Free Press, New York.
8. Porter, M. E. (1996), "What is strategy", *Harvard Business Review*, November-December, pp. 61-78.
9. Stacey, R. D. (2000), *Strategic management and organizational dynamics: The Challenge of complexity*, Pearson Education Ltd., England.
10. Wadajkar, Vishal; Kumar, Atul and Brar, Vinaydeep (2016), "Positioning, Performance, Problems and Prospects of Digital Marketing firms in India", *International Journal of Enhanced Research in Science, Technology & Engineering*, Vol. 5, Issue 12, pp. 131-138.
11. Walker, J. (2004), *Modern competitive strategy*, McGraw Hill Companies, New York.

ABOUT THE AUTHOR (S)

Dr. Somnath Patil is an Associate Professor, Dr. D. Y. Patil Institute of Management and Research, Pune, Maharashtra, India

Mr. Vishal Wadajkar is an Assistant Professor, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India